

USAGE OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: As a compulsory subject in the curriculum of English language classes a task was set before secondary schools. Foreign language teachers create conditions for introducing foreign language to younger students acquiring skills.

Keywords: communicate, secondary school, classroom, GTM, riddles, childhood, conversation, children.

It is generally believed that the school-aged children have a strong interest in learning a language. Especially, children of this age have high memorization ability. Secondary school children can be taught to communicate through interesting methods. CLT is the result of new demand in learning and teaching English. GTM had been dominant for a long time before the introduction of CLT. Many linguists claim that learning a language will be more effective with following natural methods. It is not clear, approaches to Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) for Older Learners suitable for young English learners. Therefore, this articles seeks to take a critical view consider communicative language teaching to determine eligibility classroom practice for high school students. CLT focuses on the development of communicative competence extensive use of the target language in learning and competence in practice process, often in situational contexts.

The complexity of this task is possible explained by the fact that only a part of high school student educational and cognitive process and many qualities necessary for success educational activities in the acquisition of foreign language communication in infancy.

One of the qualities is the presence of communicative skills among school children is to successfully form the ability to communicate in a foreign language taking into account the speaking abilities and needs of students of elementary level this age group. In this regard, the process of teaching foreign language in schools should be built in such a way as to make a maximum contribution to its

development. Use of questionnaires and interview methods in data collection the researcher consulted 24 students and 6 teachers, which is (80%) and (20%) respectively in which 54% of respondents were aware of the CLT method and directly agreed. The second was how the communicative method of language teaching is used in secondary schools research objective. To achieve this goal, the researcher recruited 30 students 80% of them were students and 20% were teachers. The researcher created the questionnaires and interview questions that all respondents are required to complete and answer these tasks. In carrying out this task, the researcher divided language learning practices into two categories indoor and outdoor language learning practices. CLT method can be applied to ensure successfulness in English language learning in secondary schools. 28 out of 30 respondents (93.3%) pointed out their suggestions on how CLT can be applied in enabling successful learning processes among secondary school students. They had this to say; Teachers should be facilitators rather than instructors, Initiation of Training and Seminars, Creation of Favorable Learning Environment, Increasing Participation in Supervising English language learning Programs, Establishing More English Speaking and Learning Programs and Providing Motivation and Rewards to teachers and learners.

In fact, Role playing is an effective activity that is often used in the CLT classroom. For example, some students may love to shop, so the teacher decides that they should discuss their love of shopping through a role play. One student acts as a cashier and the other as a customer. Through this role-playing game, two students can act out a conversation they often hear between cashiers and customers in real life, such as what the weather is like, how their day is going, what brings them to the store comes and is asked too much.

Interviews are also a great way to use CLT in the classroom. For example, students can be put into groups and ask each other about their interests, such as their hobbies. The teacher can then ask students to share what they learned from each peer by giving a brief description of another student's hobby and why. This allows students to repeat what they have heard, but allows them to work in an informal, low-level collaboration where they don't feel like they are learning on their own. Group discussions and pair discussions are effective ways to prioritize student interaction, creating a more open and safe environment. When students are listening to a teacher's lecture, they may not retain the information if they are asked to practice their skills in a less successful way, such as through a group discussion. When students point out their mistakes, such as grammar

mistakes they make on a worksheet, they may feel as if they are unable to learn on their own. When they are put in groups or asked to practice the language with others, they can see that they are not alone in the process of learning a new language. Therefore, our imaginations learning process and what is the appropriate style for the young learner may need to be re-examined. Caution is required when accepting assignments and communication concepts and CLT principles such as activities such as authenticity and functional use of English may require reconceptualization for young learners.

The paper concludes that to create a model of the child's foreign language appropriate approaches to communication and learning/teaching, which is required provide descriptions of language use both in and out of the classroom a classroom that reflects the realities of the child's world and language learning. CLT was an innovation that was welcomed and widely adopted. Therefore, he has influenced English language teaching and classroom practice around the world. However, like all radical changes in established practice. The discussion will focus primarily on the concept itself, the communicative competence(CC). Secondary school learners in Japan are situated in a different reality from adult language users for whom the notion of CC was originally devised. They live elsewhere culture and society from native speaking children, European children and others Asian children. Japanese children are expected to function in different cultures and cultures social contexts. To make the issue, society and technology is changing rapidly and communication is changing accordingly, with the idea apparently a variable ability. However, that doesn't mean we shouldn't try to clarify or even define the concept of CC for the young reader.

Indeed, education systems around the world have focused on English for young people students of recent years. In recent pedagogy, task-based language teaching (TBLT), a type of CLT widely accepted, stimulating, and enabling real connection. Tasks were originally introduced for adult students a second language should be used outside the classroom. Therefore, the main element in the creation of tasks was an attempt to bring real-life situations class, the desire to achieve practical goals through use from real materials. Some of the secondary children have limited reasons for use the language for practical purposes and spend a lot of time on the game. Children enjoy language games involving repetition, rhythm and nonsense words. Such linguistic features are felt in songs, chants and rhymes. Very young children are primarily guided by sound rather than meaning. They enjoy playing language even if they don't understand the meaning.

In using GTM to teach English, the lesson is teacher-centered and in that learning environment, students are not so active and flexible. Whereas in a CLT classroom, the focus is on the students, the students allowed to be at the center of the teaching and learning process. This means that students in CLT classes earn initiative in classroom activities, because the more they work in CLT lessons. Each method has its own strengths and weaknesses, and the actual application can cause problems in a particular context. With its goals, key features and principles, CLT is a good way to go development of communication skills of high school students.

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